

Compounding of Offences and the Powers of the Commissioner General in Tax Dispute Settlement: An Appraisal

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Abstract:

The effectiveness of tax administration depends on a legal and regulatory framework that promotes fairness, transparency, and efficient dispute resolution. In Tanzania, one mechanism adopted to address tax offences is compounding, which allows the Commissioner General of the Tax Revenue Authority (TRA) to settle offences administratively by imposing fines instead of pursuing prosecution. Compounding enables offenders to settle liabilities without facing trial. However, the legal structure governing compounding raises questions regarding fairness, consistency, and suitability as a genuine form of alternative dispute resolution (ADR). The study employed a qualitative research approach. It also uses a doctrinal methodology where various sources of legal materials, including Acts, regulations, books, and journal articles, among others, were reviewed, alongside structured interviews with 20 respondents, including TRA officials, legal experts, taxpayers who experienced compounding, and university lecturers in tax law. The findings identified challenges affecting the credibility of compounding as an ADR mechanism, such as the absence of a neutral facilitator, broad discretionary powers of the Commissioner General, lack of clear statutory guidelines, weak institutional capacity, and limited appeal mechanisms. The study recommends legislative and administrative reforms, including clear eligibility criteria, internal review mechanisms, enhanced transparency, and strengthened coordination, to transform compounding into a credible, fair, and effective ADR mechanism within Tanzania's tax system.

Keywords: Tax Offences, Compounding, Alternative Dispute Resolution, Tax Disputes, Legal Framework, Tanzania.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Compounding of tax offences represents a significant administrative mechanism within tax enforcement system in Tanzania, allowing certain offences to be settled without resorting to lengthy criminal proceedings.¹ The approach is intended to promote efficiency in tax administration by enabling taxpayers who admit liability to resolve their cases through payment of a prescribed amount, thereby saving time and resources for both the taxpayer and the Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA).² In theory, this process aligns with the broader goals of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) by promoting cooperation and voluntary compliance between taxpayers and the authority.³ However, the practice of compounding in Tanzania raises important questions regarding fairness and the balance of power within the process. The Commissioner General of the TRA holds extensive authority to decide whether or not an offence may be compounded, and to determine the terms upon which such compounding shall occur. While this discretion is rooted in law, concerns have emerged over the absence of procedural safeguards and the limited opportunities for taxpayers to participate meaningfully in the decision-making process.⁴

Data for this study were collected through doctrinal and empirical methodologies. The doctrinal approach involved a documentary review of statutes, regulations, books, journal articles, and research papers on tax law and administration. To complement the doctrinal analysis, empirical data were collected through structured interviews of 20 respondents, including six TRA officers, six legal practitioners, six taxpayers who had experienced compounding and two academicians. The collected data were analysed thematically and doctrinally to interpret legal provisions, institutional practices, and practical experiences. This article therefore examines the regulatory dimensions of compounding as a tax dispute settlement mechanism in Tanzania, with particular emphasis on the scope and implications of the Commissioner General's powers, and assesses its effectiveness as a genuine alternative to tax dispute resolution.

2. BRIEF HISTORY OF TAXATION IN TANZANIA

Taxation in Tanzania dates back to the colonial era under the German administration, which introduced direct taxes such as the hut, poll, and head taxes to push Africans into the monetary economy rather than to raise substantial revenue.⁵ The British trusteeship that followed in 1919 marked a decisive phase in the evolution of the tax system. The

¹ H B Kiunsi, 'Watching the Watcher: Evaluating the Tanzania Revenue Authority in its administration of tax' (2021) 28(1) *Huria: Journal of the Open University of Tanzania*. 19.

² A A Saheed, 'Towards an effective regime of the application of condonation, compounding of offences and plea bargaining as veritable alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms' (2023) 8(1) *ABUAD Law Journal* 139 <https://doi.org/10.53982/alj.2020.0801.09-j> accessed 6 November 2025.

³ *Ibid.*

⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵ E Kitime and D Mwamlangala, *Laws of Taxation in Tanzania* (Institute of Finance Management 2017) 6.

British introduced income tax in 1940, largely affecting Europeans, while Africans continued to be taxed indirectly through customs and excise duties.⁶ Later, the creation of the East African High Commission in 1948 and the enactment of the East African Income Tax (Management) Act of 1952 and its 1958 revision sought to harmonise taxation across Kenya, Uganda, and Tanganyika. These reforms introduced principles of residence and source-based taxation, laying the groundwork for a modern fiscal structure.⁷ After the collapse of the East African Community in 1977, Tanzania enacted the Income Tax Act of 1973, later replaced by the Income Tax Act of 2004 to modernise and consolidate its domestic tax regime in line with international standards.⁸

As the tax system evolved, the compounding of offences gradually emerged as an administrative tool to address non-compliance. Under the Income Tax Act 2004,⁹ Part IX (Division V) provided for “Compounding Offences” in section 119. Instead of prosecuting every tax offender, authorities were allowed to settle certain offences through compounding, whereby a taxpayer could admit wrongdoing and pay a fine in lieu of prosecution.¹⁰ Although this mechanism was intended to foster compliance and reduce court congestion, it initially lacked a coherent legal framework and was characterised by wide administrative discretion, resulting in inconsistencies and concerns about fairness.¹¹ The need for structured regulation became evident as the number of tax disputes increased, demanding a system that could deliver both efficiency and accountability.¹²

A turning point occurred in 2015 with the enactment of the Tax Administration Act,¹³ which consolidated the management of all major tax laws and introduced a formal legal basis for compounding offences. Section 106 of the Act empowered the Commissioner General of the Tanzania Revenue Authority to compound offences upon a taxpayer’s written admission, marking a shift toward recognising compounding as part of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) in tax administration. The subsequent Tax Administration (General) Regulations of 2016,¹⁴ and later amendments in 2019, sought to standardise procedures, introduce documentation requirements, and curb abuse of

⁶ O Kibuta, *Tax Compliance in Tanzania: Analysis of Law and Policy Affecting Voluntary Taxpayer Compliance* (Mkuki na Nyota Publishers Ltd 2011) 8.

⁷ F D A L Makinyika, *A Sourcebook of Income Tax Law in Tanzania* (1st edn, Dar es Salaam University Press 2000) 8.

⁸ E Kitime and D Mwamlangala, *Laws of Taxation in Tanzania* (Institute of Finance Management 2017) 6.

⁹ Income Tax Act, No. 11 of 2004.

¹⁰ B M Saiteu, *Tax Law and Practice in Tanzania* (Jursi Publisher Limited 2023) 167.

¹¹ A A Saheed, ‘Towards an effective regime of the application of condonation, compounding of offences and plea bargaining as veritable alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms’ (2023) 8(1) *ABUAD Law Journal* 139 <https://doi.org/10.53982/alj.2020.0801.09-j> accessed 6 November 2025.

¹² *Ibid.*

¹³ Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

¹⁴ Tax Administration (General) Regulations, GN No. 101 of 2016.

discretion. Nonetheless, gaps persisted particularly concerning excessive discretion, lack of appeal mechanisms, and limited transparency in decision-making.¹⁵

This paper therefore examines the compounding of offences as an alternative to tax dispute settlement in Tanzania, focusing on the scope and impact of the Commissioner General's powers and assessing its effectiveness as a genuine ADR mechanism.

3. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ADR AND COMPOUNDING OF TAX OFFENCES

Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) refers to mechanisms that allow disputes to be settled outside traditional court processes through methods such as mediation, conciliation, negotiation, and arbitration.¹⁶ The central aim of ADR is to provide flexible, cost-effective, and timely means of resolving disputes while preserving relationships between parties. In the context of taxation, ADR serves as a cooperative tool that enables tax authorities and taxpayers to resolve conflicts in a manner that maintains compliance, fairness, and administrative efficiency.¹⁷ Compounding of tax offences shares similar goals with ADR. It allows a taxpayer who has committed a tax offence to admit the wrongdoing, pay a fine, and settle the matter without undergoing criminal prosecution. This process reduces litigation and promotes quick recovery of government revenue while maintaining the taxpayer's ability to continue business operations. In this sense, compounding reflects the essential philosophy of ADR, which favours amicable settlement over punitive confrontation.¹⁸

Both ADR and compounding are guided by common principles that include voluntariness, fairness, confidentiality, finality, and cost-effectiveness. In both processes, the parties resolve the matter by mutual agreement rather than through coercive court procedure.¹⁹ Voluntariness is particularly vital, as it ensures that the party admitting to the offence does so freely and with full understanding of the implications. Fairness and confidentiality are equally important in maintaining trust between the parties, while finality ensures closure and avoids repetitive litigation.²⁰

Despite these shared principles, ADR and compounding differ in their structure and scope. ADR generally involves an independent or neutral facilitator, such as a

¹⁵ O Kibuta, *Tax Compliance in Tanzania: Analysis of Law and Policy Affecting Voluntary Taxpayer Compliance* (Mkuki na Nyota Publishers Ltd 2011) 8.

¹⁶ Mashamba JC, *Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in Tanzania: Law and Practice* (Mkuki na Nyota 2013) 14.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸ Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), *Study into the Role of Tax Intermediaries* (OECD Publishing 2008). 19.

¹⁹ Lovenheim P, *Mediate, Don't Litigate: How to Resolve Disputes Quickly, Privately, and Inexpensively Without Going to Court* (Nolo Publishers 2004) 33.

²⁰ Lovenheim P, *Mediate, Don't Litigate: How to Resolve Disputes Quickly, Privately, and Inexpensively Without Going to Court* (Nolo Publishers 2004) 21..

mediator or arbitrator, whose role is to guide discussions and help the parties reach a mutually acceptable solution.²¹ Compounding, on the other hand, is usually administered solely by a competent authority such as the Commissioner General in tax matters. In this case, the tax authority performs both administrative and quasi-judicial functions, making the process more formal and regulatory in nature than other ADR forms.²² Another distinguishing feature lies in the type of disputes they address. ADR typically handles civil and commercial disputes, focusing on issues of interpretation, breach of contract, or administrative disagreements.²³ Compounding, in contrast, deals specifically with criminal or quasi-criminal tax offences where an offence has already occurred but prosecution can be avoided through settlement. This makes compounding both a compliance tool and an administrative remedy that complements rather than replaces ADR.²⁴

In terms of procedural framework, ADR is often flexible and guided by the principles of party autonomy. Parties can determine the form, language, and outcome of the proceedings.²⁵ Compounding is more rigid since it is governed by statutory provisions that prescribe steps such as issuing a notice of offence, written admission, fine determination, and the issuance of a compounding order. While ADR allows broader negotiation on outcomes, compounding is confined to the statutory limits set by taxation laws.²⁶

The similarities between ADR and compounding are found mainly in their objectives and outcomes. Both aim to reduce the burden on courts, encourage cooperative compliance, and save public resources. They also provide certainty and finality once an agreement or order is issued.²⁷ In both cases, the matter is considered settled and cannot be reopened except under exceptional circumstances such as fraud or procedural irregularity. This ensures administrative efficiency and stability in legal relations.²⁸ From a policy perspective, both mechanisms promote a culture of dialogue and self-regulation. ADR enhances public trust by demonstrating that justice can be achieved without confrontation, while compounding encourages taxpayers to take responsibility for their

²¹ Leah N Mnzava, 'Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tax Ombudsman Offices: A Comparative Analysis on Legal and Institutional Framework in Tanzania Mainland' (2024) 7 IJLMH 666–681.

²² A A Saheed, 'Towards an effective regime of the application of condonation, compounding of offences and plea bargaining as veritable alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms' (2023) 8(1) ABUAD Law Journal 139 <https://doi.org/10.53982/alj.2020.0801.09-j> accessed 6 November 2025.

²³ Lovenheim P, *Mediate, Don't Litigate: How to Resolve Disputes Quickly, Privately, and Inexpensively Without Going to Court* (Nolo Publishers 2004) 36.

²⁴ Leah N Mnzava, 'Alternative Dispute Resolution in Tax Ombudsman Offices: A Comparative Analysis on Legal and Institutional Framework in Tanzania Mainland' (2024) 7 IJLMH 666–681.

²⁵ Mashamba JC, *Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in Tanzania: Law and Practice* (Mkuki na Nyota 2013) 18.

²⁶ Eva Komba, 'Tax Administration and Due Process Concerns in Tax Enforcement in Tanzania' (2021) 25 *Journal of Contemporary African Legal Studies* (forthcoming). 11.

²⁷ Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, *Study into the Role of Tax Intermediaries* (OECD Publishing 2008). 27. ISBN 978-92-64-04179-0

²⁸ *Ibid.*

actions and settle disputes through administrative cooperation. In this regard, compounding complements ADR by adapting its philosophy to the field of tax administration.²⁹

However, ADR is broader in scope and is widely used in multiple sectors such as commercial, labour, and family disputes,³⁰ whereas compounding remains confined to tax enforcement. Nonetheless, both embody the shift from adversarial to cooperative justice, reflecting modern governance ideals that prioritise efficiency, participation, and fairness.³¹ Thus, compounding of tax offences in Tanzania functions as a specialised form of ADR designed to achieve similar objectives of resolving disputes efficiently, promoting voluntary compliance, and maintaining administrative harmony. Although it operates within a statutory framework, its underlying principles are consistent with the spirit of ADR. Together, both systems illustrate the evolution of dispute resolution towards more consensual, transparent, and participatory models of justice.

4. LEGAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK ON TAX AND DISPUTE SETTLEMENT IN TANZANIA

The legal framework governing tax and dispute settlement in Tanzania comprises various laws and regulations that collectively guide the administration, collection, and resolution of tax-related matters. On the other hand, the regulatory framework encompasses the institutions responsible for implementing these laws, collecting taxes, and handling disputes when they arise.³² The principal tax laws include the Tax Administration Act,³³ which provides the general procedures for tax administration and enforcement; the Value Added Tax Act;³⁴ the Income Tax Act;³⁵ and the East African Community Customs Management Act, which governs customs operations within the East African Community. Other important legislations are the Tanzania Revenue Authority Act,³⁶ the Tax Revenue Appeals Act,³⁷ the Tax Revenue Appeals Board Rules, the Tax Revenue Appeals Tribunal Rules, the Appellate Jurisdiction Act,³⁸ and the Court of Appeal Rules. Collectively, these laws provide the statutory foundation for the assessment, collection, enforcement, and dispute resolution of taxes in Tanzania, ensuring that both taxpayers and authorities operate within a clear and predictable legal framework.

²⁹ B M Saiteu, *Tax Law and Practice in Tanzania* (Jursi Publisher Limited 2023) 170.

³⁰ N S Ndoboka and C K Mtaki, 'Enforceability of the principle of party autonomy in court-annexed mediation in mainland Tanzania' (2024) *Journal of Legal Studies & Research* 51.

³¹ *Ibid.*

³² R J Mukama, *Regulation of Primary SACCOs in the Context of Enhancing Credit Advancement in Mainland Tanzania* (PhD Thesis, Mzumbe University 2023) 60.

³³ *Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.*

³⁴ *Value Added Tax Act, Cap. 148 R.E. 2023.*

³⁵ *Income Tax Act, Cap. 332 R.E. 2023.*

³⁶ *Tanzania Revenue Authority Act, Cap. 399 R.E. 2023.*

³⁷ *Tax Revenue Appeals Act, Cap. 408 R.E. 2023.*

³⁸ *the Appellate Jurisdiction Act, Cap. 141 R.E. 2023.*

The Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA) serves as the primary regulatory body overseeing tax matters in Tanzania. It was established under Section 4 of the Tanzania Revenue Authority Act³⁹ and began operations on 1 July 1996.⁴⁰ The TRA is mandated to administer and enforce revenue laws, assess and collect government revenue, and advise the government on fiscal and tax policy matters. It performs key functions such as coordinating the administration of tax laws, promoting voluntary compliance, combating tax evasion, and ensuring effective collection of taxes, fees, and levies. The Authority is headed by the Commissioner General, who is established under Section 16 of the same Act. The Commissioner General exercises wide administrative and enforcement powers, including the assessment and recovery of taxes, issuance of agency notices, granting tax amnesty, determining objections, and compounding of offences under Section 106 of the Tax Administration Act.⁴¹ These powers enable the TRA to manage tax disputes efficiently and reduce the need for prolonged litigation.

In the tax dispute resolution hierarchy, several institutions play critical roles. The Tax Revenue Appeals Board (TRAB), established under Section 3 of the Tax Revenue Appeals Act,⁴² is the first appellate body that hears and determines disputes between taxpayers and Commissioner General of the TRA. Its decisions may be appealed to the Tax Revenue Appeals Tribunal (TRAT), created under Section 7 of the same Act, which serves as a higher forum for reviewing the Board's decisions. Further appeals on points of law may be taken to the Court of Appeal of Tanzania, operating under the Appellate Jurisdiction Act⁴³ and the Court of Appeal Rules. Collectively, these institutions constitute the regulatory framework for tax administration and dispute settlement in Tanzania. They ensure that taxpayers have access to administrative and judicial remedies while promoting fairness, transparency, and accountability in tax governance. The next section covers various tax offences that arise as a result of breach of tax laws.

5. TAX OFFENCES

The primary law governing tax offences in Tanzania is the Tax Administration Act.⁴⁴ The Act provides a comprehensive framework outlining different forms of non-compliance and misconduct that amount to offences under the tax regime. Sections 93 to 105 of the Act describe offences ranging from simple administrative failures to deliberate acts of evasion or fraud. For example, Section 93 criminalises failure to comply with tax laws, which may occur when a taxpayer refuses to maintain proper records or disregards

³⁹ Tanzania Revenue Authority Act, Cap. 399 R.E. 2023.

⁴⁰ B Mutakyawa, 'Tax Compliance and Enforcement in Tanzania: An Appraisal of the Tax Administration Act' (2019) *Eastern Africa Law Review* 46 17.

⁴¹ Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁴² Tax Revenue Appeals Act, Cap. 408 R.E. 2023.

⁴³ Appellate Jurisdiction Act, Cap. 141 R.E. 2023.

⁴⁴ Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

instructions from the Commissioner General.⁴⁵ Similarly, Section 94 makes it an offence to fail to pay tax within the prescribed time, an act that directly undermines government revenue collection.⁴⁶

A common and serious offence arises under Section 95, which deals with the making or use of false or misleading statements or documents. In practice, this often occurs when a taxpayer intentionally inflates deductible expenses or fabricates invoices to reduce taxable income.⁴⁷ For instance, a business may claim input VAT for purchases that never took place, or submit falsified receipts to secure tax refunds. These actions not only distort tax assessments but also constitute criminal misconduct under the Act. Another example is provided under Section 97, which criminalises failure to use fiscal devices.⁴⁸ This happens when traders, especially in retail businesses, conduct sales without issuing fiscal receipts or tamper with fiscal devices to conceal the actual volume of transactions. Such practices deny the government substantial revenue and violate statutory obligations under the Act.⁴⁹

The Act also covers offences by authorised and unauthorised persons under Section 98, addressing misconduct by tax officers or external agents engaged in tax administration. Section 99 extends liability to corporate entities whose directors or managers participate in or permit offences to be committed in the course of business.⁵⁰ Importantly, Section 100 makes clear that payment of tax remains mandatory even when a person is convicted or when an offence is compounded, meaning that criminal liability does not extinguish the underlying tax debt. In addition, Sections 101 to 105 outline general penalties and specific offences relating to VAT, stamp duty, and excise duty, reinforcing the government's determination to ensure full compliance with fiscal obligations.⁵¹

Judicial interpretation has further strengthened the application of these provisions. In *Director of Public Prosecutions v. Hassan Abdalla Mitawi & Another*,⁵² the Court of Appeal considered the evidentiary standard required to establish tax offences. The accused were charged with tax evasion and abuse of office, but the Court acquitted them on the ground that the prosecution failed to prove its case beyond reasonable doubt. The Court held that mere suspicion, however strong, cannot substitute proof when establishing offences under Sections 93 to 96. This ruling reaffirmed that the criminal enforcement of tax law must adhere to strict evidentiary requirements. Similarly,

⁴⁵ Section 93 of the Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁴⁶ Section 94 of the Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁴⁷ Section 95 of the Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁴⁸ Section 97 of the Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁴⁹ N S Ndoboka and C K Mtaki, 'Enforceability of the principle of party autonomy in court-annexed mediation in mainland Tanzania' (2024) *Journal of Legal Studies & Research* 51.

⁵⁰ Sections 98 and 99 of the Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁵¹ Section 100 and 105 of the Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁵² *Director of Public Prosecutions v. Hassan Abdalla Mitawi & Another* (Criminal Appeal No. 82 of 2023).

in *Jacks (Tanzania) Limited v. Commissioner General, Tanzania Revenue Authority*⁵³ the Court upheld the TRA's decision to disallow input VAT claims for transactions deemed fictitious and lacking commercial substance. While the matter was civil, it reflected the close relationship between administrative enforcement and criminal liability under Sections 95 and 96, which deal with false statements and impeding tax administration. The decision underscored that fraudulent documentation or deliberate concealment can not only trigger administrative sanctions but also amount to criminal offences.⁵⁴

Through these statutory and judicial developments, it becomes clear that tax offences in Tanzania represent serious violations of public duty and financial accountability. Their enforcement demands both procedural fairness and strict adherence to evidentiary standards. The next section examines how these offences interact with the compounding of offences mechanism under the same Act, which serves as an alternative means of resolving tax violations without resorting to full criminal prosecution.

6. COMPOUNDING OF TAX OFFENCES

Compounding offences often occurs after the breach of tax laws which amounts to tax offences as noted in the section above. In this situation, a taxpayer who has committed an offence is given an opportunity to settle the matter administratively without facing prosecution.⁵⁵ Compounding of offences is a legal mechanism that allows a taxpayer who has committed an offence to avoid prosecution by paying a prescribed fine together with any tax, interest, and penalties due under the law.⁵⁶ It serves as an administrative settlement option intended to encourage voluntary compliance and reduce the burden of criminal proceedings. Under the Tax Administration Act,⁵⁷ the power to compound offences rests with the Commissioner General of the TRA and his delegated officers who have jurisdiction over the matter. Section 99 of the Act provides that any offence under Part X(d) of the Act may be compounded by the Commissioner General either before or after the commencement of prosecution proceedings. This provision reflects the flexibility of the compounding process, allowing taxpayers to regularize their position even after enforcement action has begun.⁵⁸

It is important to note that compounding of offences is not a right vested in taxpayers. Rather, it is a discretionary remedy granted by the Commissioner General upon consideration of specific factors, including the conduct of the taxpayer, the

⁵³ *Jacks (Tanzania) Limited v. Commissioner General, Tanzania Revenue Authority* (Civil Appeal No. 529 of 2023).

⁵⁴ Section 95 and 96 of the Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁵⁵ A A Saheed, 'Towards an effective regime of the application of condonation, compounding of offences and plea bargaining as veritable alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms' (2023) 8(1) ABUAD Law Journal 139 <https://doi.org/10.53982/alj.2020.0801.09-j> accessed 6 November 2025.

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*

⁵⁷ Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

seriousness of the offence, and the surrounding circumstances.⁵⁹ The Commissioner General may approve compounding only if the taxpayer pays all outstanding amounts, including the tax liability, interest, penalties, and compounding charges.⁶⁰ In addition, the taxpayer must withdraw any pending appeals or objections relating to the matter being compounded. The objective of this procedure is to promote administrative efficiency and ensure that revenue is recovered promptly without lengthy litigation.⁶¹ However, the Commissioner General retains the authority to accept or reject applications for compounding, and refusal must be accompanied by reasons and an opportunity for the taxpayer to be heard.⁶²

The Tax Administration (General) Regulations,⁶³ as amended, outline the procedure for compounding of offences in Part XI. Under Regulation 99, when the Commissioner General reasonably believes that a person has committed an offence, a notice of offence must be served using the form prescribed in the Thirteenth Schedule.⁶⁴ The notice includes the name, address, and Taxpayer Identification Number (TIN) of the offender, the particulars of the offence, and the period within which the offender must respond in writing under section 92 of the Act. The offender may, under Regulation 100, apply for the offence to be compounded within seven days from the date of the notice by submitting a written request in the prescribed form along with an admission of the offence and acceptance of the proposed terms of compounding. The Commissioner General must determine the request within thirty days and, if satisfied, issue a compounding order in the form provided in the Fifteenth Schedule.⁶⁵

When determining the amount payable, the Commissioner General considers the fine prescribed under the Act and the extent of cooperation and disclosure made by the offender. A taxpayer who fully cooperates and truthfully discloses all relevant facts may be granted immunity from prosecution for the compounded offence.⁶⁶ However, if the Commissioner General rejects the application, the taxpayer must be given an opportunity to be heard, and the reasons for rejection must be recorded.⁶⁷ Once a compounding order is finalised and the payment made, the taxpayer cannot subsequently claim a refund or

⁵⁹ W C Gomera, G Oreku and I Shau, 'Enhancing tax administration to micro businesses through digital technology: An exploratory study in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania' (2021) 17(23) *European Scientific Journal* 39 <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2021.v17n23p39> accessed 6 November 2025.

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*

⁶¹ M Epaphra, 'Tax rates and tax evasion: Evidence from missing imports in Tanzania' (2023) 7(2) *International Journal of Economics and Finance* 122 <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijef.v7n2p122> accessed 6 November 2025.

⁶² A A Saheed, 'Towards an effective regime of the application of condonation, compounding of offences and plea bargaining as veritable alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms' (2023) 8(1) *ABUAD Law Journal* 139 <https://doi.org/10.53982/alj.2020.0801.09-j> accessed 6 November 2025.

⁶³ Tax Administration (General) Regulations, GN No. 101 of 2016.

⁶⁴ Regulation 99 of the Tax Administration (General) Regulations, GN No. 101 of 2016.

⁶⁵ Regulation 100 of the Tax Administration (General) Regulations, GN No. 101 of 2016.

⁶⁶ B M Saiteu, *Tax Law and Practice in Tanzania* (Jursi Publisher Limited 2023) 167.

⁶⁷ *Ibid.*

deny the commission of the offence. This position was affirmed in the Indian case of *Shamrao Bhagwantrao Deshmukh v. Dominion of India*,⁶⁸ where it was held that a person who voluntarily compounds an offence cannot later repudiate the settlement.

Where a person fails to respond to the notice of offence or does not apply for compounding within the prescribed time, Regulation 101 empowers the Commissioner General to institute criminal proceedings. These prosecutions are reserved for serious violations such as deliberate tax evasion or fraudulent misrepresentation.⁶⁹ Generally, less serious non-compliance arising from misunderstanding or negligence is addressed through penalties and administrative sanctions.⁷⁰ Nevertheless, compounding serves as an alternative dispute resolution mechanism to tax disputes in Tanzania by reducing the backlog of cases before courts and promoting voluntary compliance. However, its effectiveness as an alternative to formal litigation has raised concern as to whether it truly constitutes a genuine ADR. The next section evaluates the effectiveness of compounding of offences as a genuine alternative to tax dispute resolution in Tanzania.

7. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings reveal that the compounding of tax offences has become a significant mechanism within the Tanzanian tax system, serving both administrative and dispute-resolution purposes. It enables the Commissioner General of TRA to resolve certain offences without resorting to lengthy and costly court proceedings. However, despite its practical advantages in saving time and enhancing tax collection efficiency, several legal and procedural challenges have been observed in its implementation. These include:

7.1 Absence of a neutral facilitator in the compounding process

As provided under Section 106(1) of the Tax Administration Act,⁷¹ the Commissioner General is empowered to compound any offence committed under a tax law by ordering payment of a fine, forfeiture of goods, or both, provided that the taxpayer admits the offence in writing. Furthermore, Section 106(2) authorises the Commissioner General to issue a compounding order specifying the nature of the offence and the amount payable.⁷²

In addition, Regulation 99(1) of the Tax Administration (General) Regulations requires that when the Commissioner General has reasonable grounds to believe an offence has been committed, a Notice of Offence must be served to the taxpayer using the prescribed form. Regulation 100(1) allows the taxpayer to apply for compounding within seven days, while Regulation 100(4) obliges the Commissioner General to determine such application within thirty days.⁷³ Once the application is granted, the compounding process is carried

⁶⁸ *Shamrao Bhagwantrao Deshmukh v. Dominion of India*, [1955] 27 ITR 30 (SC).

⁶⁹ Regulation 101, GN No. 101 of 2016.

⁷⁰ B M Saiteu, *Tax Law and Practice in Tanzania* (Jursi Publisher Limited 2023) 167.

⁷¹ Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁷² Section 106 of the Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁷³ Regulation 100, Tax Administration (General) Regulations, GN No. 101 of 2016.

out under the facilitation of the Commissioner General, who oversees the implementation of the agreed terms and payment of the prescribed fine. These provisions collectively place the Commissioner General in a position to act both as the enforcing party representing the TRA and as the authority deciding on the matter, thereby combining investigative and adjudicative roles.

In practice, the Commissioner General serves both as a party to the dispute and as the authority responsible for deciding it. This dual role undermines the neutrality expected in any fair and balanced resolution process. Respondents from different groups, including taxpayers, legal practitioners, and academicians, shared concerns that this structure leaves taxpayers with limited confidence that their cases are handled impartially.⁷⁴ It was noted that since TRA is both the accuser and the decision-maker, taxpayers often feel compelled to comply with whatever terms are proposed without meaningful negotiation or the opportunity to be heard fairly.⁷⁵ The situation was described as one where compounding, rather than promoting mutual understanding, is seen as a compliance enforcement tool controlled entirely by the authority.⁷⁶

TRA officials, however, defended this arrangement, explaining that the Commissioner General's authority in compounding arises directly from the law and is meant to promote efficiency rather than to act as a forum for adversarial resolution.⁷⁷ It was emphasised that the process helps to expedite cases and recover government revenue without going through lengthy court procedures.⁷⁸ Despite this, the majority of respondents maintained that the process would gain greater legitimacy and acceptance if it incorporated a neutral facilitator, such as an independent mediator or conciliator, who could balance the interests of both parties.⁷⁹ The study therefore found that the absence of such neutrality undermines the essence of ADR and remains a fundamental challenge to recognising compounding as a genuine alternative dispute resolution mechanism in Tanzania.

7.2 Broad legal authority and discretion of the commissioner general

The study found that another pressing challenge in the compounding of tax offences is the broad discretionary power given to the Commissioner General under section 106 of

⁷⁴ Interview with a representative of a manufacturing company (taxpayer), Sayona Drinks Limited, Dar es Salaam, 16 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁷⁵ Interview with a senior legal officer, Apex Attorneys, Dar es Salaam, 15 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁷⁶ Ibid.

⁷⁷ Interview with the Commissioner for Customs and Excise, Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), Dar es Salaam, 15 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁷⁸ Interview with a Legal Officer, Legal Services Department, Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), Dodoma, 10 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁷⁹ Interview with a finance manager from a logistics and trading company (taxpayer), Mohammed Enterprises Tanzania Limited (MeTL), Dar es Salaam, 16 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

the Tax Administration Act.⁸⁰ This provision authorises the Commissioner to compound an offence by imposing a fine, ordering forfeiture of goods, or both, once the taxpayer admits the offence in writing. In practice, however, the findings revealed that the exercise of this power depends largely on the Commissioner's personal discretion. Several taxpayers reported that even after admitting the offence and submitting a request to compound, their applications were rejected.⁸¹ They expressed concern that the law does not guarantee the right to compound an offence once applied for, making the process appear uncertain and unpredictable.⁸² This experience has led to a perception among many taxpayers that the decision to allow or deny compounding depends more on administrative discretion than on established legal criteria.⁸³

From the perspective of TRA officials, the discretionary authority serves an important purpose. They explained that it allows the Commissioner to consider each case individually, taking into account the seriousness of the offence, the taxpayer's level of cooperation, and the potential impact on revenue collection.⁸⁴ They argued that this flexibility helps the Authority reach practical and fair outcomes without lengthy court proceedings.⁸⁵ However, legal practitioners and academicians interviewed during the study cautioned that this level of discretion, if not guided by transparent standards, risks inconsistent decision-making and weakens public trust in the mechanism.⁸⁶ They emphasised that predictability and fairness are fundamental features of any credible alternative dispute resolution system and called for clear criteria to guide the exercise of the Commissioner's discretion in compounding tax offences.⁸⁷

7.3 Lack of clear statutory guidelines and criteria

The legal provisions governing the compounding of tax offences in Tanzania are inadequately detailed, leaving too much discretion in the hands of the Commissioner General. Section 106 of the Tax Administration Act⁸⁸ authorises the Commissioner General to compound offences by ordering payment of fines or forfeiture once a taxpayer admits the offence in writing. However, the section does not define the specific offences eligible for compounding, the criteria for determining fines, or the parameters for verifying voluntary admissions. Likewise, Regulations 99 to 105 of the Tax

⁸⁰ Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁸¹ Interview with a representative of a business entity (taxpayer), Tanzania Startup Association, Dar es Salaam, 16 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁸² Interview with a representative of a manufacturing company (taxpayer), Sayona Drinks Limited, Dar es Salaam, 16 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁸³ Ibid.

⁸⁴ Interview with a Senior Manager, Revenue Collection and Risk Control Department, Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), Dar es Salaam, 15 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁸⁵ Interview with a Senior Officer, Compliance and Investigation Department, Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), Dodoma, 10 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁸⁶ Interview with a managing partner, IMMMA Advocates (DLA Piper Africa – Tanzania), Dar es Salaam, 15 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁸⁷ Ibid.

⁸⁸ Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

Administration (General) Regulations,⁸⁹ outline the procedural flow from issuance of the Notice of Offence to the Compounding Order yet they provide no objective guidance on how discretion should be exercised. For instance, Regulation 101 merely instructs that fines “shall be determined in accordance with the relevant tax law,” a phrase too general to ensure uniformity. This vagueness in the law has resulted in unequal treatment of taxpayers and undermined the predictability required for a fair administrative process.⁹⁰

Empirical findings from legal practitioners reinforced these statutory weaknesses. Advocates and tax consultants interviewed in Dar es Salaam and Dodoma observed that TRA officials interpret and apply the provisions inconsistently. Some noted that taxpayers facing similar offences receive different outcomes depending on the officer or regional office handling the case.⁹¹ Others explained that, in several instances, compounding applications were rejected without explanation, despite clear written admissions and willingness to pay. They described this as an administrative “grey area” where the absence of statutory guidance allows subjective judgment to dominate over legal certainty.⁹²

Taxpayers who participated in the study similarly expressed frustration with the lack of transparency. Many reported uncertainty about which offences could be compounded and how fines were calculated.⁹³ One respondent explained that the notice served under Regulation 99(1) only lists the offence but provides no details on how the proposed fine is determined or what factors influence the Commissioner’s decision.⁹⁴ Some taxpayers added that they were denied the opportunity to compound even after timely applications under Regulation 100(1), while others complained of delays beyond the thirty-day decision period prescribed in Regulation 100(4). This inconsistency, they argued, diminishes confidence in the system and discourages voluntary cooperation.⁹⁵

Based on these findings, the study concludes that the absence of clear statutory guidelines and uniform criteria weakens the fairness, transparency, and reliability of compounding as an ADR mechanism. Establishing specific legal standards for eligibility, fine assessment, and procedural review would ensure that all taxpayers are treated equally and that the TRA’s decisions are predictable and justifiable. Clear statutory direction would also align the Tanzanian framework with best administrative practices,

⁸⁹ Tax Administration (General) Regulations, GN No. 101 of 2016.

⁹⁰ *Ibid.*

⁹¹ Interview with a managing partner, IMMMA Advocates (DLA Piper Africa – Tanzania), Dar es Salaam, 15 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁹² Interview with a partner and head of corporate/tax practice, REX Attorneys, Dar es Salaam, 14 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁹³ Interview with a partner and head of corporate/tax practice, REX Attorneys, Dar es Salaam, 14 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁹⁴ Interview with a finance manager from a logistics and trading company (taxpayer), Mohammed Enterprises Tanzania Limited (MeTL), Dar es Salaam, 16 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

⁹⁵ Interview with a representative of a manufacturing company (taxpayer), Sayona Drinks Limited, Dar es Salaam, 16 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

strengthening compounding as a credible and accountable form of alternative dispute resolution in tax administration.⁹⁶

7.4 Weak institutional capacity and inconsistency

The Tax Administration Act⁹⁷ and the Tax Administration (General) Regulations, 2016, empower the Commissioner General of the TRA to administer the compounding of offences. Section 106 of the Act, read together with Regulations 99 to 105, outline the procedures for issuing notices, receiving applications, and granting compounding orders. However, these provisions place full administrative responsibility on the TRA without establishing a clear institutional structure or oversight framework to ensure consistent implementation across offices.⁹⁸ The law does not require standardised internal procedures, periodic reporting, or inter-departmental review, leaving wide room for administrative discretion and inconsistency.⁹⁹ This legislative gap weakens the institutional capacity of the TRA to deliver a uniform, transparent, and predictable compounding process, undermining the purpose of the mechanism as a credible ADR framework.¹⁰⁰

Empirical data collected from legal practitioners and taxpayers further revealed the extent of this weakness. Several legal practitioners interviewed in Dar es Salaam observed that there is no uniform interpretation of the compounding procedures among TRA officers.¹⁰¹ They explained that in some cases, regional offices issue compounding notices promptly and engage taxpayers professionally, while others delay the process or apply procedures inconsistently.¹⁰² One legal respondent highlighted that taxpayers facing similar offences often receive different treatment depending on the regional office handling the matter, creating perceptions of administrative bias.¹⁰³

Taxpayers interviewed during the study expressed similar frustrations. Many complained that the compounding process depends heavily on the officer's personal interpretation rather than a clear institutional standard.¹⁰⁴ Some taxpayers noted that, in Dodoma and Dar es Salaam, certain TRA officers were cooperative and resolved cases quickly, while others demanded unnecessary documentation or delayed issuing

⁹⁶ Ibid.

⁹⁷ Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

⁹⁸ Section 106 of Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023, and Regulation 99 to 105 of the 2016 Regulation.

⁹⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰⁰ Ibid.

¹⁰¹ Interview with a partner and head of corporate/tax practice, REX Attorneys, Dar es Salaam, 14 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹⁰² Ibid.

¹⁰³ Interview with a partner and head of corporate/tax practice, REX Attorneys, Dar es Salaam, 14 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹⁰⁴ Interview with a finance manager from a logistics and trading company (taxpayer), Mohammed Enterprises Tanzania Limited (MeTL), Dar es Salaam, 16 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

compounding orders for months. This inconsistency, according to several taxpayers, erodes confidence in the system and discourages voluntary compliance.¹⁰⁵

Both groups: legal practitioners and taxpayers agreed that the absence of internal monitoring and capacity-building measures within TRA contributes to these inefficiencies. Legal experts emphasised that regular training on ADR principles, standardised internal procedures, and the establishment of a dedicated compounding or settlement unit would strengthen institutional capacity and ensure uniform application of the law. Without such reforms, the effectiveness of compounding as an ADR mechanism remains undermined by administrative inconsistency and weak institutional coordination.¹⁰⁶

7.5 Unclear relationship between compounding and other tax remedies

Another challenge identified by the study is the unclear relationship between the compounding mechanism and other tax remedies such as objections, appeals, and voluntary disclosure. Under the Tax Administration Act,¹⁰⁷ section 51(1) provides that a person who is aggrieved by a tax decision made by the Commissioner General may object to that decision by filing an objection within thirty days from the date of service of the decision.¹⁰⁸ Section 52(1) empowers the Commissioner General, upon admission of the objection, to either amend or refuse to amend the assessment or decision, while section 53(1) allows a person aggrieved by an objection decision or other decision or omission of the Commissioner General under Part VII to appeal to the Tax Revenue Appeals Board established under the Tax Revenue Appeals Act.¹⁰⁹ However, neither the Act nor its regulations specifies how the compounding mechanism interacts with these remedies, whether it can be pursued alongside an objection or appeal, or whether the lodging of an objection or appeal precludes compounding.

Empirical findings revealed that this ambiguity has caused practical confusion among taxpayers and even among officers of TRA. Several taxpayers interviewed reported being advised differently by TRA officials, with some encouraged to apply for compounding while others were informed that once an objection or appeal is filed, compounding is no longer available.¹¹⁰ Legal practitioners noted that this inconsistency undermines predictability and places taxpayers at a disadvantage, as they are often

¹⁰⁵ Interview with a finance manager from a logistics and trading company (taxpayer), Mohammed Enterprises Tanzania Limited (MeTL), Dar es Salaam, 16 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid.

¹⁰⁷ Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

¹⁰⁸ Section 51 of the Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

¹⁰⁹ Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

¹¹⁰ Interview with a representative of a manufacturing company (taxpayer), Sayona Drinks Limited, Dar es Salaam, 16 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

uncertain about which option best protects their interests.¹¹¹ Some taxpayers described cases where they began the compounding process only to be informed later that their matter could not proceed because an objection had already been filed, causing unnecessary delays and frustration.¹¹²

TRA officers who participated in the study acknowledged that the law provides limited direction on the sequencing or compatibility of these remedies. While some officers viewed compounding as an entirely separate administrative process distinct from the objection and appeal framework,¹¹³ others considered it a complementary mechanism that could operate before or in parallel with formal remedies, depending on the nature of the offence. This lack of shared understanding among officials reinforces procedural inconsistency and weakens the coherence of the overall tax dispute-resolution framework.¹¹⁴ The study found that this ambiguity undermines the effectiveness of compounding as a reliable ADR mechanism. Without clear statutory guidance on how compounding relates to other remedies, both taxpayers and administrators face uncertainty, which increases procedural delays and reduces public confidence in the fairness and predictability of the system.

7.6 Finality and lack of appeal

Another major challenge affecting the credibility of compounding as an alternative dispute resolution mechanism, namely the issue of finality and the lack of an appeal or review process. Section 106(3)(d) of the Tax Administration Act¹¹⁵ provides that a compounding order “shall be final and not subject to appeal,” meaning that once the Commissioner General compounds an offence and issues an order, the taxpayer cannot challenge that decision through the ordinary tax appeals system. According to TRA officials interviewed, this provision is intended to promote administrative efficiency and legal certainty by preventing endless disputes and ensuring that once a taxpayer admits to an offence and settles the corresponding fine, the matter is conclusively closed.¹¹⁶ They further noted that in practice, this principle aligns with how most ADR mechanisms function, since ADR decisions such as arbitration awards and conciliation settlements are often final and binding.¹¹⁷ In that sense, compounding resembles an ADR process, as it

¹¹¹ Interview with a partner and head of corporate/tax practice, REX Attorneys, Dar es Salaam, 14 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹¹² Interview with a finance manager from a logistics and trading company (taxpayer), Mohammed Enterprises Tanzania Limited (MeTL), Dar es Salaam, 16 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹¹³ Interview with a Senior Manager, Revenue Collection and Risk Control Department, Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), Dar es Salaam, 15 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹¹⁴ Ibid.

¹¹⁵ Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

¹¹⁶ Interview with an Officer, Enforcement Division, Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), Dodoma, 10 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹¹⁷ Interview with a Senior Officer, Taxpayer Services and Education Department, Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), Dar es Salaam, 15 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

provides a final settlement between the tax authority and the taxpayer without resorting to the courts.

However, many legal practitioners, academicians, and taxpayers who participated in the study expressed concern that the absence of any internal or independent review mechanism undermines fairness and transparency. Respondents pointed out that judicial review, the only available remedy under the current legal framework, is a difficult and costly process that focuses on procedure rather than substantive fairness.¹¹⁸ This creates the perception that once the Commissioner General issues a compounding order, the taxpayer's right to redress is practically closed.¹¹⁹

Judicial precedents have consistently confirmed the finality of compounding orders. In *Commissioner General (TRA) v. Mohamed Al-Salim & Omary Hassan*,¹²⁰ the Court of Appeal held that compounding orders are not appealable to the Tax Revenue Appeals Board and can only be challenged by judicial review in the High Court. Similarly, in *TRA v. JSC Atomredmetzoloto & Others*,¹²¹ the Court reaffirmed that the Tax Revenue Appeals Board lacks criminal appellate jurisdiction to hear appeals arising from compounding, as such matters fall outside its statutory mandate. The Court reasoned that section 219(3)(e) of the East African Community Customs Management Act, a provision similar to section 106(3)(d) of the Tax Administration Act, renders compounding orders final and not subject to appeal, allowing them to be enforced as if they were High Court orders.

In practice, both the Tax Revenue Appeals Board (TRAB) and the Tax Revenue Appeals Tribunal have maintained this interpretation, frequently striking out appeals challenging compounding decisions. For instance, in *Islam Salehe Nahid v. Commissioner General (TRA)*¹²² and *Rungwe Freight (T) Ltd v. Commissioner General (TRA)*,¹²³ the appeals bodies reaffirmed that compounding orders are final and beyond their jurisdiction. Likewise, in *Vic Fish Ltd v. Commissioner General (TRA)*,¹²⁴ the Tribunal stressed that while compounding orders are final, the Commissioner General must follow the correct procedures, including serving a proper notice of offence before issuing an order. The Tribunal described any compounding done without adherence to these procedures as unjust, reinforcing that compounding, though administrative, must still meet standards of fairness.

¹¹⁸ Interview with a partner and head of corporate/tax practice, REX Attorneys, Dar es Salaam, 14 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹¹⁹ Ibid.

¹²⁰ *Commissioner General (TRA) v. Mohamed Al-Salim & Omary Hassan*, Civil Appeal No. 80 of 2018 [2019] TZCA 647 (Court of Appeal of Tanzania, 29 April 2019).

¹²¹ *TRA v. JSC Atomredmetzoloto & Others*, (Court of Appeal of Tanzania, 16 April 2019).

¹²² *Islam Salehe Nahid v. Commissioner General (TRA)*, (Commercial Case No. 19 of 2009) [2009] TZHC 601 (14 December 2009).

¹²³ *Rungwe Freight (T) Ltd v. Commissioner General (TRA)*, (TRAT 2002).

¹²⁴ *Fish Ltd v. Commissioner General (TRA)*, (TRAT, reported 2 TTLR 46).

Thus, while the finality of compounding promotes efficiency and legal certainty and reflects a key characteristic of ADR mechanisms, the study found that it also limits access to justice and weakens public confidence in the mechanism.¹²⁵ The absence of an internal review process, coupled with the procedural complexity and high cost of judicial review, creates a perception that the process is one-sided.¹²⁶ Therefore, although compounding possesses ADR-like features such as finality and efficiency, its effectiveness as a fair and balanced ADR mechanism remains limited by the lack of impartial oversight and procedural safeguards.

7.7 Interaction with the Director of Public Prosecutions

The study reveals that the requirement for the Director of Public Prosecutions (DPP) to give consent before compounding can proceed once criminal charges have been filed plays a significant role in maintaining oversight in the handling of tax offences.¹²⁷ This provision, embedded in section 106(3) of the Tax Administration Act,¹²⁸ was described by TRA officials as an important safeguard that ensures only appropriate cases are compounded and that serious offences with potential criminal implications remain under prosecutorial scrutiny. According to officials interviewed, this collaboration helps maintain checks and balances between the TRA and the DPP, preventing the misuse of compounding powers and reinforcing accountability within the process.¹²⁹

However, several legal practitioners and academicians pointed out that, in practice, the process of obtaining the DPP's consent is often unclear and time-consuming. They observed that there is no publicly available guideline outlining the procedures, timelines, or communication channels to be followed when seeking such consent.¹³⁰ This lack of clarity sometimes causes unnecessary delays and uncertainty, undermining the efficiency of compounding as an alternative dispute resolution mechanism.¹³¹ Taxpayers interviewed during the study similarly reported that these delays discourage them from applying for compounding once they learn that the process may depend on further approvals outside the TRA.¹³² Some even indicated that by the time consent is obtained,

¹²⁵ Interview with a partner and head of corporate/tax practice, REX Attorneys, Dar es Salaam, 14 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹²⁶ *Ibid.*

¹²⁷ Section 106(4) of the Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023, and Regulation 104 of the Tax Administration (General) Regulations, GN No. 101 of 2016.

¹²⁸ Tax Administration Act, Cap. 438 R.E. 2023.

¹²⁹ Interview with a Senior Manager, Revenue Collection and Risk Control Department, Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), Dar es Salaam, 15 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹³⁰ Interview with a partner and head of corporate/tax practice, REX Attorneys, Dar es Salaam, 14 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹³¹ Interview with a Senior Lecturer, University of Dar es Salaam (UDSM), School of Law, Dar es Salaam, 6 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹³² Interview with a finance manager from a logistics and trading company (taxpayer), Mohammed Enterprises Tanzania Limited (MeTL), Dar es Salaam, 16 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

criminal proceedings are already underway, leaving them with limited options to settle administratively.¹³³

The study also noted other practical challenges related to the compounding process. For instance, taxpayers must apply for compounding within seven days of receiving the notice of offence, otherwise they lose the right to compound under Regulation 100(2) of the Tax Administration (General) Regulations. Moreover, the law prohibits compounding after prosecution has commenced unless the DPP's consent is granted.¹³⁴ The requirement of a written voluntary admission, while intended to ensure fairness and transparency, can also create challenges where allegations of coercion or undue influence arise. In *Al-Salim*,¹³⁵ the defendants argued that their confessions had been obtained through duress, but the Court ruled that such challenges could only be raised through judicial review, not by appeal. Additionally, section 106(4) of the Tax Administration Act provides that compounding only settles the offence and its associated penalty it does not extinguish the taxpayer's underlying tax liability or interest. TRA officers confirmed that even after compounding, taxpayers are still required to pay any outstanding taxes, and failure to do so triggers normal enforcement procedures.

8. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section concludes and recommends for the improvement of the current system of compounding offences as a mechanism for resolving tax disputes in Tanzania. The study concluded that compounding of offences plays a crucial role in resolving tax disputes efficiently and promoting compliance with tax laws without the need for formal litigation. It allows taxpayers to correct their non-compliance by paying an agreed composition amount, which helps reduce the administrative and judicial workload on both the TRA and the courts. However, the practice raises significant concerns regarding transparency, fairness, and accountability, particularly due to the broad discretionary powers vested in the Commissioner General and the absence of clear procedural safeguards or avenues for appeal. These shortcomings affect the perception of justice and undermine the credibility of compounding as a genuine alternative to tax dispute resolution. Therefore, strengthening the legal and procedural framework governing compounding is essential to ensure it functions as a fair, transparent, and effective mechanism for tax dispute settlement in Tanzania.

¹³³ Interview with a representative of a manufacturing company (taxpayer), Sayona Drinks Limited, Dar es Salaam, 16 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹³⁴ Interview with a Senior Lecturer, University of Dar es Salaam (UDSM), School of Law, Dar es Salaam, 6 September 2025, interview conducted by the researcher.

¹³⁵ Commissioner General, Tanzania Revenue Authority v Mohamed Al-Salim & Omary Ally Hassan, Civil Appeal No. 80 of 2018 [2019] TZCA 647 (Court of Appeal of Tanzania, 29 April 2019).

